

Nazarin Kasantacciyar Kwalliya Cikin Suratul Baƙara Da Al-Imran (Fassarar Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi)

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Tsakure

Wannan Maƙala ta yi nazarin kasantacciyar kwalliyar magana wadda ta fito a cikin fassarar Hausa ta Alkur’ani Maigirma na Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi. An gudanar da nazarin a cikin suratul Baƙara da Al-imran. Manufar binciken shi ne fito da nau’o’in kasantacciyar kwalliyar magana waɗanda suka dace da ra’in Lakoff da Johnson (1980) a kan mahanga ta tunani. An yi amfani da hanyar Kalailaicewa ta sharhi domin samar da sahihin bincike. Sakamakon bincike ya nuna cewa ana iya samun nau’o’in kasantacciyar kwalliyar magana a cikin surorin biyu waɗanda suka dace da ra’in Lakoff da Johnson. Haka nan ana iya yin nazarinsu dangane da tunani ta yadda ake samar da alaƙa a tsakanin tushen tunani da makarɓar tunani. Sannan kuma ana samun wasu kalamai a cikin hirar Hausawa ta yau da kullum waɗanda suka dace da kwalliyar managar.

Gabatarwa

Harshen Hausa kamar sauran harsuna na duniya, harshe ne da yake cike da hikimomi da adon harshe a cikinsa. Don haka da wuya a lokacin da mutum yake magana ko rubutu ya kasance ba tare da tsarma wani nau’i na adon harshe ba, don cimma manufa. Dalilin haka wannan takarda ta nazarci fassarar Alkur’ani da Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi ya yi domin fito da kwalliyar harshe a cikin fassarar. Kamar yadda a cikin kowane irin harshe ake samun adon harshe da sauran fannonin harshe, haka a harshen Hausa ma ake da su, waɗanda har aka yi amfani da su cikin fassarar Alkur’ani da Sheikh Gumi ya yi.

Nazarin furucin kwalliya ya samu tagomashi a inda aka nazarci shi a harsuna da dama a duniya cikinsu har da Alkur’ani mai girma. Kasancewar cike yake da hikimomi da balagar harshe wanda kwalliya tana ɗaya daga cikinsu. Da haka ne Almajir (2011:67) ya bayyana furucin kwalliya da cewa:

“Furucin kwalliya wata magana ce da ake yi bisa irin fahimta da ake da ita ta wani abu, sai a yi zancen wani abin daban, wanda a tsakanin abubuwan biyu akwai kamanceceniya ko wata ‘yar alaƙa ta wata fuskar”.

A wannan bincike an yi nazarin nau’i ɗaya ne kawai daga cikin ire-iren kwalliya kamar yadda Lokoff da Johnson (1980) suka bayyana. Wato, kasantacciyar kwalliya/kwalliyar kasancewar yadda abu yake. An fito da ire-iren nau’o’inta tare da fito da misalai da suka fito a cikin Suratul Baƙara da Al-imran. An yi bayanin su dalla-dalla.

Domin samun nasarar wannan bincike an yi amfani da hanyar Kalailaice fassarar Alkur’ani mai girma musamman a surorin da aka ambata. An karanci fassarar surorin a lokuta daban-daban. A karo na farko an karanta, yayin da a karatu na biyu aka zaƙulo inda nau’o’in kwalliyar suka fito. A karatu na uku kuma aka karkasa su dangane da irin nau’in da kowacce ta faɗa, sannan aka yi bayaninsu dalla-dalla.

A wannan bincike an yi amfani da ra’in Lakoff da Johnson (1980) a matakin tunani. Ra’in yana magana ne a kan yadda furucin kwalliya, wanda ya ginu a kan irin tunanin da ɗan’Adam yake

da shi da kuma irin kamanci na tushe da kuma na al’ada da abubuwan biyu da ake kamantawa a matsayin *tushen tunani* da *makarbar tunani* suke da su. Wannan ne yake bayar da damar zaɓar *makarbar tunani* wanda za a yi amfani da shi a fahimci *tushen tunani*. Evans da Green (2006) cewa suka yi “*makarbar tunani* tana samar da wata siga a furucin kwalliya. Wannan siga tana samuwa ne ta hanyar duba sassan furucin kwalliyar guda biyu. Hakan na samuwa ne idan aka kalli sassan biyu ta la’akari da furucin kwalliya da suka fito. Wato dai a alaƙantasu a mataki na tunani”. Wannan fassarar bincike ne.

Shi kuwa Langacker (2006:108) cewa ya yi:

“*Tunani wanda ya shafi furucin kwalliya abu ne wanda ba za a iya kauƙe masa ba a cikin zancen yau da kullum, don haka sai mu saki jiki mu amfana da shi*”. (fassarar mai bincike).

Kwalliya Ta Yadda Abu Ya Kasance/Kasantacciyar Kwalliya (Ontological Metaphor)

Kwalliyar kasancewar yadda abu yake/kasantacciyar kwalliya fanni ne na ilmin falsafa wanda ya shafi yanayin yadda abu yake kasancewa. Wato bai wa abu wata sifa wadda a zahirance ba ta dace da shi ba ko kuma abu ne wanda ba kasantacce ba amma a nuna ya kasance. Misali kamar a ce ya faɗa kogin soyayya, domin a zahiri ba a ganin soyayya balle a ce har mutum ya faɗa cikin ta. A nan an ba wa soyayya siffar wani abu na zahiri, bayan ita ba ganin ta ake ba. Hakan na nuni da yin amfani da nau’in kwalliya ta maƙunshi. Wannan nau’in kwalliya ita ma ta ƙunshi rassa kamar haka; akwai (i) kwalliya ta maƙunshi (ii) kwalliya ta abu (iii) kwalliya gagara ƙirga.

Kwallita Ta Maƙunshi (Container Metaphor)

Kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau’i ce ta kasancewar yadda abu ya kasance/kasantacciyar kwalliya a inda akan gabatar da wani abu wanda ba a gani ko a taɓa ko a ji shi a matsayin yana da ciki da waje kuma ana iya zuba wani abu ko a ɗebo wani abu a cikinsa. Lakoff da Johnson (1980) sun kasa ta gida huɗu, akwai (i) kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau’in yanayi/hali (container state metaphor) da (ii) kwalliyar maƙunshi nau’in aiki (container action metaphor) da (iii) kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau’in taro (container event metaphor) da kuma (iv) kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau’in zirga-zirga (container activity metaphor) ga bayanana su daki-daki kamar haka:

Kwalliya ta Maƙunshi Nau’in Yanayi/Hali, (Container, State Metaphor) misali

1. ... kuma idan kun kasance a cikin SHAKKÀA ga abin da muka saukar (2:23).
A nan an nuna ‘*shakkàa*’ a matsayin maƙunshi wanda za a iya shiga ko a fita daga cikinsa. A zahiri kuwa, shakka ba a ganin ta har a shiga cikinta. Kalmar shakka aba ce wadda take nuni ga hali ko yanayi da mutum ya kasance a ciki. Kasancewar an ce ‘cikin shakka’. Wannan ya nuna cewa an yi amfani da kwalliya nau’i mai nuna yanayi ko halin da aka kasance a ciki dangane da kwalliya ta tunani. Misali kamar a ce ‘jariri a cikin mahaifiyarsa’, ‘Yaro a cikin mota’ da makamantan su. Waɗannan duka ana iya ganin su a zahiri kuma har a iya shiga cikinsu. Hakan ya yi daidai da yadda Hausawa kan ce ‘ka saka ni cikin shakka’.
2. Haƙuri a *cikin* TSANANII (2:177).
Haƙiƙa nan ma an yi amfani da kwalliya ta maƙunshi, inda aka nuna ‘tsanani’ a matsayin wani abu wanda za a iya gani kuma a shiga cikinsa. Misali kamar yadda mutum yake iya shiga cikin ɗaki ko mota. A zahiri kuwa ‘tsanani’ abu ne wanda ba ganinsa ake yi ba, sai dai mutum ya samu kansa a wannan hali ko yanayi. Ashe ke nan ‘tsanani’ jin sa kawai ake yi a jiki ba ganin sa ba. Kamar yadda aka ce ‘masu haƙuri a cikin tsanani, watau tsanani shi ne maƙunshin da masu haƙuri za su shiga ciki. Haƙuri kuma shi ne abin da za a shigar a ciki. Wannan ya nuna an yi amfani da kwalliya ta maƙunshi tsarin yanayi ko halin da ake ciki. Domin, Hausawa a cikin maganganunsu na yau da kullum suna cewa ‘mun shiga tsanani a wannan zamani’.

Kwalliya ta Maƙunshi Nau'in Aiki, (Container, Action Metaphor)

3. ... kuma ku cika ALƘAWARII na (2:40).

Wannan fassarar ta nuna alƙawari kamar wani maƙunshi ne wanda zai iya ɗaukar wani abu a zuba har a cika maƙunshin, ke nan ana iya ganinsa a fili. A zahiri kuwa alƙawari abu ne wanda ba ganinsa ake yi ba. Hasalima wani aiki ne da mutum yake aiwatarwa wanda yake nuna cikas kamar mutum. Saboda haka, a nan an yi amfani da kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau'in aiki. Misali kamar ace 'a ɗebo ruwa a cika bokiti', wanda a zahiri da ruwan da bokitin duka ana iya ganinsu har a taɓa su. A nan Alƙawari shi ne aka yi amfani da shi a matsayin bokiti wato maƙunshin da za a cika ruwa a cikinsa. Kamar yadda Hausawa kan ce 'na cika alƙawarin da na ɗauka ko alƙawarinmu ya cika cif'.

4. ... waɗanda suka yaƙe ku a *cikin* HANYAR Allah (2:190).

Hanya a nan kwalliya ce ta alamci (Mytonomy) wadda take nufin hanyar Allah kamar wani maƙunshi ne wanda za a iya shiga cikinsa, Kuma da aka ce 'hanya' ba ana nufin hanya ce kamar titi wanda mota da dabbobi da mutane suke bi ta kai ba, wanda ake iya gani da idanu ba. Hanyar Allah ba a ganinta a zahiri, sai dai tana nuni ga ayyukan ɗa'a wanda Allah yake so. Yaƙi aiki ne wanda ake aikata shi a aikace. Saboda haka, ba za a iya ɗaukar yaƙi a saka shi a cikin hanya ba. A nan an yi amfani da kwalliyar magana wadda take nuni zuwa aikata wasu ayyuka na ɗa'a domin samun rabauta. Hanya a nan ba ana nufin wadda za a iya bi a kanta ba.

Kwalliya ta Maƙunshi Nau'in Taro, (Container, Event Metaphor)

5. ... Yana fitar da su daga DUFFAI zuwa ga HASKÈE (2:257).

Wannan fassarar ta nuna *duhuu* da *haskèe* kamar wasu abubuwa ne waɗanda ake iya taɓawa har a iya shigar da ɗaya cikin ɗaya. *Haske* a nan ya zama kamar wani maƙunshi ne wanda za a iya sanya wani abu a cikinsa. A zahiri kuwa haske da duhu dukkaninsu abubuwa ne waɗanda ido ke iya tantancewa, amma kuma ba a iya ɗaukar su ko a shiga cikinsu. Kasancewar an samu ayyuka mabambanta a ciki kamar fita daga duhu da shiga cikin haske an nuna cewa an yi amfani da kwalliya ta maƙunshi. Misali kamar inda ake samun taron mutane ko wata kaɓila ko ayarin mutane su fita daga kafirci shi ne a matsayin duhuu, shigan su musulunci shi ne haske. Haka abin yake idan muka kalli yadda 'yan wata jam'iya suke yin gungu su fita daga jam'iya su koma wata jam'iyar wanda suke wa laƙabi da wankan tsarki. Wato dai su fita daga gurbatacciya jam'iya zuwa jam'iya mai nagarta. A maganganun yau da kullum Hausawa suna cewa 'Allah ya yaye maka duhun jahilcin da kake ciki. Allah ya shigar da shi hasken musulinci'.

6. ... sai ku yi tsere zuwa ga ayyukan **alheri** (2:748).

A nan an nuna kalmar **alheri** kamar wani maƙunshi ne wanda za a iya zuwa gare shi kuma har a shiga cikinsa. A zahiri aikin alheri abu ne wanda ba ganinsa ake yi da ido ba, ballantana a taɓa shi ko a shige shi ba. Kalmar alheri kalma ce dundulalliya wadda ta tattara abubuwa da dama a cikin ta waɗanda suke kusantar da bawa (mutum) zuwa ga ubangijinsa, misali kamar sadaka da ambatan Allah da tausayi da makamantansu. Dangane da haka ne al'umma take rigegeniya wajen aikatasu. Kowanne yana son samun rabauta. Ba wai ana nufin gudu ba, amma himman yin aiki na ƙwarai. Kamar yadda Hausawa kan ce 'Jumma babbar rana. Ranar da wani yake kera wani, ba da gudu ba sai da ambaton Allah'.

Kwalliya ta Maƙunshi Nau'in Zirga-Zirga, (Container, Activity Metaphor)

7. ... ku shiga cikin MUSULUNCII gaba ɗaya (2:208)

A nan ma da aka ce 'ku shiga cikin musulunci' shi musulunci ɗin nan a ina yake? Ai ba ganinsa ake ba ballantana har a tafi zuwa gare shi a shiga ciki. Wannan ne ya nuna samun kwalliya ta maƙunshi dangane da ra'in Lakoff na tunani. A zahiri, musulunci abu ne wanda ya ƙunshi yin

ayyuka daban-daban a cikinsa, kamar sallah da alwala da aikin hajji da ba da zakka da azumi da sauransu. Domin haka, ba za a ce a shige shi ba, sai dai a ce a gudanar da dukkan nau’o’in ibada da suke a musulunci. Misali in muka dauki sallah kafin a gudanar da ita sai an yi tsarki sannan a yi alwala sannan kuma a tafi zuwa ga masallaci domin gudanar da ita sallar. Haka nan aikin hajji ya kunshi zirga-zirga iri daban-daban kamar dawafi da jifan shaidan zuwa filin arfa da kuma safa da marwa da makamantansu. Wannan shi ne ya nuna samun kwalliya ta makunshi reshen zirga-zirga/kai-kawo a cikin wannan fassara. Domin, Hausawa kan ce John ya shiga musulunci.

8 ... to suna *cikin SAABAANII* kawai (2:137)

A wannan aya, an yi amfani da kwalliya ta makunshi, kamar yadda aka nuna sabani a matsayin abu wanda ake iya gani har a shiga cikinsa. Misali kamar a ce ‘sun shiga cikin daki ko cikin akwati ko cikin kaya da makamantansu’. Amma a zahiri, shi sabani ba a ganinsa, nuni kawai yake da wata zirga-zirga ko kai-kawo a tsakanin abubuwa biyu. A nan ana nufin an samu rashin fahimta a tsakanin mutane biyu. Duba da wannan shi ne ya nuna cewa haƙiƙa an yi amfani da kwalliya ta makunshi reshen zirga-zirga a cikin wannan fassarar. Domin daga cikin maganganun yau da kullum Hausawa kan ce ‘shekararsu biyar cikin sabani sai yau suka shirya’.

Kwalliya ta Abu (Entity Metaphor)

Kwalliya ta abu, fanni ne na kwalliyar kasancewar yadda abu ya kasance a inda wani abu wanda ba a ganinsa ko a taɓa shi ko a ji shi yake wakiltar wani abu wanda yake na zahiri. Irin tunanin da muke da shi game da abubuwa na zahiri kan ba mu damar fahimtar abubuwa. Haka nan, fahimtarmu dangane da abubuwa waɗanda suke na zahiri, shi ke ba mu damar faɗaɗa tunaninmu kan abubuwan da za mu iya gani mu taɓa ko mu iya karkasa su ko mu sanya su cikin rukuni-rukuni ko kuma mu iya auna su. Ga misalin yadda take kasancewa kamar haka:

9.

a) Kuma kada ku lulluɓe GÀSKIYAA da KÀRYÀA (2:42)

b) ... Don me kuke lulluɓe GÀSKIYAA da KÀRYÀA (3:71)

Haƙiƙa kalmomin **gaskiya** da **karya** a cikin fassarar, an nuna su a matsayin abu wanda za a iya taɓa shi kuma abu ne na zahiri, duba da kalmar **lulluɓe**. Wannan kalma ta **lulluɓe** ita ta nuna hakan. A waɗannan ayoyi an yi amfani da kalmar *gaskiya* a matsayin wani abu da za a iya taɓawa har a dauke shi a rufe wani abu da shi. Ita kuma *karya* ita ce abin da za a lulluɓe. Misali kamar a ce a lulluɓe yaro da bargo. A zahiri kuwa **karya** da **gaskiya** su ne suke da halaye waɗanda ke nuna nagarta ko rashin nagartar mutum. Misali, Hausawa kan ce ‘ya riƙi gaskiya ya ajiye karya’.

10. a. ... waɗanda suka sayi KÀAFIRCII da IMANI (3:77)

b. ... wanda yake SAYAR da RANSA domin Allah ... (2:207).

Kalmar sayar a wannan fassara ita ta nuna RAI a matsayin wani abu na zahiri wanda za a iya ma kimanta adadinsa matuƙar dai har za a sayar da shi ko a saya. Misali kamar tufafi ko kayan masarufi da makamantan su ana iya cewa na sayar, ya sayar da gidansa ko na sayar da kayan. Don haka, wannan ya zama kwalliya mai nuna kasancewar yadda abu yake/kasantaciyyar kwalliya (ontological metaphor) kuma rukunin abu.

Kwalliya Ta Gagara-Kirga (Substance Metaphor)

Kwalliya gagara-kirga nau'i ne na kwalliyar kasancewa a inda wani abu wanda ba na zahiri ba kamar; taro ko aiki ko sosuwar rai ko tunani aka nuna shi a matsayin wani abu kamar gari ko ruwa ko mai, wato dai abin da ba za a iya kirga shi ba.

Ga misalin yadda take kasancewa kamar haka:

11. ... kuma aka cikawa kowane RÂI sakamakon abin da ya tsirfanta (3:25).

A wannan fassarar an bai wa 'rai' siffar wani abu wanda ake iya ganinsa a zahiri har a taba shi. Misali kamar gari ko gishiri ko tsaba da makamantansu. Kasancewar abubuwa waɗanda ake iya auna su har a cika wani abu da shi. Kamar a cika bokiti da ruwa ko kwarya da gari. A zahiri kuwa 'rai' ba a ganinsa balle har a taba shi. Sai dai an yi amfani da wannan kwalliya ne domin a nuna cewa dukkan abin da mutum ya aikata mai kyau da marar kyau zai tarar da shi a ranar lahira.

12. ... *masu cika* ALKAWARII idan sun kulla (2:117).

'Alkawari' wani abu ne wanda ake furta shi da baki kawai, amma ba a ganinsa, balle a taba shi ko a iya saka shi ko cika shi cikin wani abu. Amma sai aka yi amfani da tsarin kwalliya ta gagara kirga, inda aka nuna alƙawari a matsayin wani abu kamar yashi wanda za a iya dɓa, a cika shi a cikin wani abu har ma a iya kulla shi. Wannan ya tabbatar da samun kwalliya a wannan fassara.

13. ... Ya Ubangiji ka zuba HAKURI a kanmu (2:250)

'Hakuri' wani abu ne wanda ɗan'Adam ba ya iya ganin sa, ballantana har ya taba shi. Sai dai kawai idan mutum yana da wasu ɗabi'u ko halaye waɗanda suke nuni da iya mallakar zuciyarsa, sai a ce 'wane yana da hakuri'. Amma a cikin wannan fassara sai aka yi amfani da wannan tsari na kwalliya gagara kirga, domin a nuna 'hakuri' a matsayin wani abu wanda ake iya gani ko a taba kamar ruwa ko gari ko yashi ko mai da makamantansu. Kamar a ce 'an zuba gari a kan yaro'. A nan hakuri shi ne a matsayin gari wanda aka zuba a kan yaro. Amma ana nufin Allah ba mu ikon yin hakuri da dukkan jarabawa da ta sami mutum. Kamar yadda Hausawa kan ce 'Allah ya zuba mata hakuri a zamantakewarsu da kishiyarta'.

Kammalawa

Wannan takarda ta dubi kasantacciyar kwalliya/kwalliya kasantau a cikin Suratul Baƙara da Al-Imran, inda aka fito da wasu misalai waɗanda suka yi daidai da ra'in Lakoff da Johnson (1980). Binciken ya gudana a kan iyakacin tunani da kuma fahimtar mai bincike dangane da wannan ra'i. An yi ƙoƙarin fito da ire-iren wannan kwalliya a ƙarƙashin kowane nau'i tare da bayanin yadda yake kasance. Sannan aka yi ƙoƙarin nuna yanayin yadda abu yake kasancewa. Wato bai wa abu wata siffa wadda a zahirance ba ta dace da shi ba ko kuma abu ne wanda ba kasantacce ba amma an nuna ya kasance. Hakan yana faruwa ne dangane da alaƙar da take tsakanin tushen tunani da makarɓar tunani. A jimlace an yi nasarar fito da misalai kimanin guda goma sha biyu daga cikin surorin biyu. Kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau'in yanayi ko hali (Container State Metaphor) tana da misalai guda biyu. Kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau'in aiki (Conterner Action Metaphor) tana da misalai biyu. Kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau'in taro (Container, Event Metaphor) tana da misalai biyu. Yayin da kwalliya ta maƙunshi nau'in zirga-zirga (container, activity

metaphor) ita ma tana da misalai biyu. Kwalliya ta abu wato (Entity Metaphor) ita ma tana da misalai guda huɗu. Sannan sai kwalliya gagara kirga (Substance Metaphor) tana da misalai guda uku.

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RATAYE

Wasu kalmomi da aka fassara dangane da abinda ya shafi wannan bincike, kamar haka:

Source – Tushen Tunani

Target – Makarɓar Tunani

Ontological Metaphor – Kasantacciyar Kwalliya/Kwalliya Kasantau

Container Metaphor – Kwalliya ta Makunshi

Container, State Metaphor – Kwalliya Makunshi Nau’in Yanayi/Hali

Container, Action Metaphor – Kwalliyar Makunshi Nau’in Aiki

Container, Event Metaphor – Kwalliya ta Makunshi Nau’in Taro

Container, Activity Metaphor – Kwalliya ta Makunshi Reshen Zirga-zirga

Substance Metaphor – Kwalliya Gagara-kirga

Entity Metaphor – Kwalliya ta Abu